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Estimation models for the aerodynamic characterisation of insect-proof screens from their geometric parameters --Manuscript Draft--

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Abstract:	<p>This study characterised the geometric and aerodynamic parameters of 35 insect-proof screens with different weft and warp threads, with porosities ranging from 0.237 to 0.556 m² m⁻². The geometric parameters were assessed by analysing digital images, and the aerodynamic parameters were determined using tests in a low-speed wind tunnel. Using the experimental measurements, four different models were developed and validated to estimate the aerodynamic parameters of an insect-proof screen from two or more of their geometric parameters: (i) to estimate the pressure drop coefficient $F\phi$ based on the thread diameter Reynolds number (Re_d) and screen porosity ϕ [m² m⁻²] $F\phi = (0.4810002 + 11.5331/Re_d) \times ((1-\phi^2)/\phi^2)$ ($R^2 = 93.9\%$ with a p-value = 0.000); (ii) estimating $F\phi$ based on the screen thickness Reynolds number (Re_t) and screen porosity ϕ [m² m⁻²] $F\phi = (0.475502 + 26.2114/Re_t) \times ((1-\phi^2)/\phi^2)$ ($R^2 = 92.1\%$ with a p-value = 0.000); (iii) estimating screen permeability $K_p = Dh^2\phi^3 / (2.0679(1-\phi)^2 + 3.8362 \times 10^{-10})$ ($R^2 = 56.3\%$ // 56.2 % with a p-value < 0.05) as a function of thread diameter D_h [m] and porosity ϕ [m² m⁻²]; (iv) estimating the inertial factor $Y = 0.0571195 + 0.135966 \cdot Dh/D_i$ ($R^2 = 58.1\%$ with a p-value = 0.0000) as a function of thread diameter [m] and the inner pore diameter D_i [m]. These models gave improved accuracy compared with the previous models described in the literature. Models for aerodynamic parameters of the insect-proof screens K_p and Y based in their geometric characteristics are very important to simulate the effects of insect screens in ventilation studies using computational fluid dynamic (CFD) studies.</p>
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Different models estimated aerodynamic characteristics from geometric parameters

Pressure drop coefficient estimated from screen porosity using Re based on thread diameter

Pressure drop coefficient also estimated from porosity and Re based on thread thickness

Permeability estimated from pore surface area or thread diameter & screen porosity

Inertial factor estimated from screen porosity or thread diameter & inner pore diameter

1 **Models for characterising the aerodynamics of insect-proof screens from their geometric**
 2 **parameters**

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11 **Abstract**

12 This study characterised the geometric and aerodynamic parameters of 35 insect-proof screens
 13 with different weft and warp threads, with porosities ranging from 0.237 to 0.556 m² m⁻². The
 14 geometric parameters were assessed by analysing digital images, and the aerodynamic
 15 parameters were determined using tests in a low-speed wind tunnel. Using the experimental
 16 measurements, four different models were developed and validated to estimate the aerodynamic
 17 parameters of an insect-proof screen from two or more of their geometric parameters: (i) to
 18 estimate the pressure drop coefficient F_φ based on the thread diameter Reynolds number (Re_d)
 19 and screen porosity φ [m² m⁻²] $F_\varphi = (0.4810002 + 11.5331/Re_d) \times ((1 - \varphi^2)/\varphi^2)$ ($R^2 = 93.9\%$ with a
 20 p -value = 0.000); (ii) estimating F_φ based on the screen thickness Reynolds number (Re_t) and
 21 screen porosity φ [m² m⁻²] $F_\varphi = (0.475502 + 26.2114/Re_t) \times ((1 - \varphi^2)/\varphi^2)$ ($R^2 = 92.1\%$ with a p -
 22 value = 0.000); (iii) estimating screen permeability $K_p = D_h^2 \varphi^3 / (2.0679 (1 - \varphi)^2) + 3.8362 \times 10^{-10}$
 23 ($R^2 = 56.3\% // 56.2\%$ with a p -value < 0.05) as a function of thread diameter D_h [m] and porosity
 24 φ [m² m⁻²]; (iv) estimating the inertial factor $Y = 0.0571195 + 0.135966 \cdot D_h/D_i$ ($R^2 = 58.1\%$ with a
 25 p -value = 0.0000) as a function of thread diameter [m] and the inner pore diameter D_i [m]. These

26 models gave improved accuracy compared with the previous models described in the literature.
27 Models for aerodynamic parameters of the insect-proof screens K_p and Y based in their
28 geometric characteristics are very important to simulate the effects of insect screens in
29 ventilation studies using computational fluid dynamic (CFD) studies.

30 **Keywords:** insect-proof screen; aerodynamic characterisation; aerodynamic model.

31 **Nomenclature**

32 **Abbreviations:**

33 *MD* Bias

34 *NSE* Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency

35 *PBIAS* Percent bias

36 *RMSD* Root mean squared deviation

37 *RSR* *RMSD*-observations standard deviation ratio

38 **Symbols:**

39 *a* and *b* Second-order polynomial regression coefficients

40 *e* Thickness [μm]

41 *n* Number of values

42 *u* Air speed [m s^{-1}]

43 *x* Direction of airflow

44 *A* and *B* Constants that depend on the type of porous material

45 *C_d* Total discharge coefficient of a greenhouse opening

46 *C_{d,φ}* Discharge coefficient due to the presence of insect-proof screens

47 *D_f* Thread density according to the manufacturer [threads cm^{-2}]

48 *D_h* Diameter of the threads [μm]

49 *D_{hx}* Diameter of the weft threads [μm]

50 *D_{hy}* Diameter of the warp threads [μm]

51	D_i	Diameter of the inside circumference of the pore [μm]
52	D_r	Thread density measurement [threads cm^{-2}]
53	F_φ	Pressure drop coefficient due to the presence of an insect-proof screen
54	K_p	Screen permeability [m^2]
55	L_{px}	Length of the pore in the direction of the weft [μm]
56	L_{py}	Length of the pore in the direction of the warp [μm]
57	P	Pressure [Pa]
58	R	Coefficient of correlation
59	R^2	Coefficient of determination
60	Re_p	Reynolds number based on the thread screen's permeability
61	Re_d	Reynolds number based on the diameter of the threads of the screen
62	Re_t	Reynolds number based on the thickness of the screen.
63	S_p	Area of the pore [mm^2]
64	Y	Inertial factor

65 **Greek Symbols:**

66	μ	Dynamic viscosity of air [$\text{kg s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-1}$]
67	φ	Porosity [$\text{m}^2 \text{m}^{-2}$]
68	β	Constant that depend on the type of porous material
69	ρ_a	Density of air [kg m^{-3}]
70	Δ	Difference

71 **Subscripts:**

72	<i>obs</i>	Values observed experimentally with wind tunnel tests
73	<i>sim</i>	Values simulated or obtained with models

74 **1. Introduction**

75 Insect-proof screens, placed in greenhouse vents, are used throughout the world to protect crops
76 against insects pests. In many regions, such as the Mediterranean, screens are normally fitted
77 to all vents in intensive greenhouse production. A recently published study showed that 99.1%
78 of farmers in the province of Almería (Spain) install insect-proof screens in all side vents, and
79 95.4% of farmers install them in the roof vents of their greenhouses (Valera *et al.*, 2016). The
80 survey showed that 58.3% of the screens installed in the vents had a thread density of 15×30
81 threads cm⁻² and 25.6% had a density of 10×20 threads cm⁻²; the percentages for roof vents
82 were 56.0% and 22.5%, respectively (Valera *et al.*, 2016). The use of these screens reduces the
83 number of insect that enter the greenhouse, thereby decreasing the need for crop protection
84 chemical treatments (Berlinger *et al.*, 1993; Taylor *et al.*, 2001; Teitel, 2007) and preventing
85 beneficial insects, such as pollinating insects (Teitel, 2007) or those used in integrated insect
86 pest management, from leaving the greenhouse.

87 Numerous studies show the disadvantages of installing these screens, which adversely affect
88 the ventilation rate of a greenhouse (defined as the number of times that the greenhouse air is
89 renewed in one hour, h⁻¹) and, therefore, its microclimate (Muñoz *et al.*, 1999; Miguel and
90 Silva, 2000; Bartzanas *et al.*, 2002; Fatnassi *et al.*, 2002, 2003 and 2006; Soni *et al.*, 2005;
91 Harmanto *et al.*, 2006; Kittas *et al.*, 2008; Teitel, 2007 and 2010; López *et al.*, 2014). Compared
92 with greenhouses without insect-proof screens, greenhouses with screens have higher
93 temperature and humidity (Bartzanas *et al.*, 2002; Fatnassi *et al.*, 2002, 2003 and 2006;
94 Harmanto *et al.*, 2006), lower air velocity (Kittas *et al.*, 2008) and a greater vertical temperature
95 gradient (Soni *et al.*, 2005); all these characteristics can adversely affect crop growth and
96 development (Kittas *et al.*, 2002; Teitel, 2010).

97 Insect-proof screens affect greenhouse ventilation flow and produces an additional pressure
98 drop to that produced by the geometry of the windows (characterised by a vent discharge
99 coefficient C_d). This pressured drop can be related to the velocity of air crossing the openings

100 (u) (Teitel, 2007; Molina-Aiz *et al.*, 2009) using only a quadratic term ($\Delta P = a u^2$) or a quadratic
101 polynomial ($\Delta P = a u^2 + b u$). In the first case, the aerodynamic behaviour of the screens is
102 characterised using only one parameter, a pressure drop coefficient (F_ϕ) but in the second case,
103 two parameters are required, permeability (K_p), that is independent of the nature of the fluid but
104 depends on the geometry of the porous medium, and an inertial factor (Y) that varies with the
105 nature of the porous medium but can be as small as 0.1 in the case of foam metal fibres (Nield
106 and Bejan, 1999). Thus, knowing the aerodynamic characteristics of insect-proof screens (F_ϕ
107 or K_p and Y) enables the effects of their use in a greenhouse with a known ventilation rate to be
108 estimated.

109 Accurate determination of the aerodynamic characteristics of insect-proof screens requires
110 either wind tunnel tests and assessment of the geometric characteristics of screens. Models have
111 been developed for estimating the pressure drop coefficient of a screen (F_ϕ) from its Reynolds
112 number based on the thread diameter (Re_d) and from its porosity (ϕ) (Hayama *et al.*, 2000;
113 Pinker and Herbert, 1967; Linker *et al.*, 2002; Bailey *et al.*, 2003). Both thread diameter (D_h)
114 and porosity (ϕ), can be determined by processing digital images of insect-proof screens
115 (Álvarez *et al.*, 2012). Porosity can be estimated using most image processing software to count
116 black and white pixels, or it can be estimated using specific software such as Euclides v1.4,
117 proposed by Álvarez *et al.* (2012). This specialist software determines screen porosity by
118 identifying the coordinates of the vertices of the screen pores, thus providing a value of screen
119 porosity while maintaining an adequate ratio between the areas of the image occupied by pores
120 and threads. The thread diameter of the screen can also be assessed through direct
121 measurements with a micrometer, but manually determining thread diameter can be a very
122 laborious task.

123 The objective of this study was to develop different models for estimating the pressure drop
124 caused by an insect-proof screen at a specific air velocity from its geometric characteristics.

125 Thus, depending on the ability to estimate geometric or other parameters, a specific model may
126 be selected to estimate the aerodynamic characteristics of an insect-proof screen. The first
127 model investigated estimated F_φ as a function of porosity (φ) and Reynolds number (Re_t) based
128 on screen thickness (e); the second model estimated F_φ as a function of porosity (φ) and
129 Reynolds number Re_d based on screen thread diameter (D_h). After estimating F_φ , a graph of
130 pressure drop as a function of air velocity can be developed. A third model was proposed for
131 estimating screen permeability (K_p) as a function of thread diameter (D_h) and porosity (φ). A
132 further model was proposed for estimating screen inertial factor (Y) as a function of thread
133 diameter (D_h) and inner pore diameter (D_i). After estimating K_p and Y , and knowing the screen
134 thickness (e), a screen pressure drop graph can be developed.

135 **2. Material and methods**

136 To develop different models for estimating the aerodynamic characteristics of an insect-proof
137 screen from only its geometric characteristics, 35 insect-proof screens with different thread
138 densities were analysed (Table 1). Insect-proof screens are manufactured with high-density
139 polyethylene (HDPE) monofilament-woven fabrics, with knot-free weft and warp threads (Fig.
140 1). This type of insect-proof screen is used in all greenhouses in the province of Almería, Spain
141 (Valera *et al.* 2016) and is the type most commonly used in greenhouses worldwide.

142

143 **Fig. 1.** Microscopic image (4×) of a 14×27 threads cm⁻² insect-proof screen

144

145 **2.1. Determining the geometric characteristics of insect-proof screens**

146 The two-dimensional geometric characteristics of insect-proof screens were assessed by
147 processing digital images acquired with a Motic DMWB1-223 microscope (Motic Spain S.L.,
148 Barcelona) equipped with a digital camera, and with a 4× calibrated microscope lens (with a
149 resolution of 10.5 μm pixel⁻¹). Three samples were analysed for each screen, acquiring 24
150 × 0.25 cm² images per sample. The method used to determine the geometric characteristics of
151 insect-proof screens is available from López *et al.* (2013). The specific software Euclides v1.4
152 (Álvarez, 2010; Álvarez *et al.*, 2012) was used to identify the vertices of each pore (Fig. 2a).
153 From these vertices, the following two-dimensional geometric parameters were obtained (Table
154 1 and Fig. 2b): D_r , measured thread density [threads cm⁻²]; ϕ , porosity [m² m⁻²]; L_{px} and L_{py} ,
155 the lengths of the pore [μm] in the weft and warp directions, respectively; D_{hx} and D_{hy} , diameter
156 [μm] of the weft and warp threads, respectively; D_h , diameter of the threads [μm]; D_i , inner
157 pore diameter [μm]; S_p , pore area [mm²]. For each image acquired, approximately 12 (for 10 ×
158 20 threads cm⁻² screens), 27 (for 14 × 27 threads cm⁻² screens) and 30 (for 13 × 30 threads cm⁻²
159 screens) pores were analysed giving a total of 864, 1944 and 2160 pores analysed per screen,
160 respectively. Álvarez *et al.* (2012) made an exhaustive analysis where they showed that three
161 randomly selected samples were sufficient to geometrically characterise these types of screen.

162

163 **Fig. 2.** Image of a 14×27 threads cm^{-2} insect-proof screen with identified pore vertices (a).

164 Geometric parameters indicated on a 10×20 threads cm^{-2} screen (b).

165

166 The thickness (e) of the insect-proof screens has been measured with a TESA-VISIO 300 device

167 (TESA SA, Switzerland; resolution of $0.05 \mu\text{m}$) through non-contact optical measurement. For

168 the magnitude of the measurements e , the uncertainty was $<10 \mu\text{m}$.

169

170 **Table 1.** Geometric characteristics of the insect-proof screens (D_f , thread density according to
171 the manufacturer [threads cm^{-2}]). Average value and standard deviation of: D_r , measured
172 thread density [threads cm^{-2}]; φ , porosity [$\text{m}^2 \text{m}^{-2}$]; L_{px} and L_{py} , the lengths of the pore [μm] in
173 the weft and warp directions, respectively; D_{hx} and D_{hy} , diameter [μm] of the weft and warp
174 threads, respectively; D_h , diameter of the threads [μm]; D_i , diameter of the inside
175 circumference of the pore [μm]; S_p , area of the pore [mm^2]; e , thickness [m].

N	D_f	D_r	φ	L_{px}	L_{py}	D_{hx}	D_{hy}	D_h	D_i	S_p	e [$\times 10^{-6}$]
1	11×23	10.4×22.2	0.322±0.008	197.0±15.1	709.5±30.5	248.2±8.4	254.4±10.6	251.3±10.3	202.0±15.1	0.140±0.012	589±7
2*	10×20	9.8×20.1	0.369±0.012	243.7±25.1	774.0±61.0	251.6±7.7	253.5±8.3	252.5±8.1	248.5±25.0	0.189±0.025	596±8
3	10×20	10.1×20.6	0.366±0.006	232.5±18.8	760.7±25.7	233.1±6.2	253.1±9.0	243.1±12.6	237.4±18.6	0.177±0.015	544±7
4	10×20	10.7×21.3	0.349±0.009	226.9±20.1	681.1±26.5	256.8±6.0	243.5±11.3	250.2±11.6	232.1±20.3	0.154±0.015	567±5
5	10×20	9.7×20.4	0.402±0.008	252.9±23.4	806.9±28.2	223.4±7.4	238.5±9.0	230.9±11.1	257.5±23.2	0.204±0.020	501±7
6	10×20	10.3×21.5	0.310±0.008	199.2±15.6	710.8±30.7	264.4±9.4	267.1±11.7	265.7±11.0	203.7±15.7	0.141±0.013	571±19
7	10×20	10.4×21.0	0.302±0.010	199.9±28.8	693.6±20.7	267.3±7.1	276.5±15.0	271.9±13.4	204.3±28.9	0.139±0.020	536±6
8	10×20	9.0×20.7	0.402±0.010	246.8±16.4	877.3±16.6	233.8±6.3	236.5±9.2	235.1±8.4	249.8±16.6	0.216±0.015	546±4
9	14×27	13.7×26.9	0.379±0.014	187.3±34.8	543.5±26.1	186.5±7.0	184.0±8.4	185.2±7.9	192.5±34.6	0.102±0.020	418±8
10	10×20	9.7×19.7	0.378±0.009	253.9±17.9	784.3±54.2	250.5±7.9	253.5±8.2	252.0±8.2	255.8±17.9	0.199±0.020	587±7
11	10×20	8.9×19.5	0.375±0.007	251.7±23.9	863.6±25.0	264.4±7.1	260.7±11.5	262.5±10.2	256.0±24.1	0.217±0.022	604±9
12	10×20	8.9×19.6	0.375±0.007	250.3±23.9	865.1±27.1	264.6±7.7	260.3±11.7	262.4±10.6	255.8±24.9	0.216±0.022	611±18
13	10×20	9.9×19.7	0.368±0.007	252.7±21.2	746.4±34.9	259.0±7.0	255.7±9.4	257.3±8.7	255.2±21.0	0.189±0.018	639±7
14	14×27	12.0×27.5	0.292±0.009	141.8±28.9	615.9±15.9	214.8±7.2	221.7±8.5	218.3±8.7	144.2±28.8	0.087±0.018	514±5
15	14×27	12.8×27.9	0.267±0.007	131.8±26.5	570.5±15.2	209.6±6.9	225.7±8.2	217.7±11.1	134.1±26.7	0.075±0.015	490±10
16	10×20	9.9×21.8	0.338±0.017	207.4±24.1	756.6±28.3	253.4±10.0	251.8±12.4	252.6±11.6	210.7±24.5	0.156±0.016	540±10
17	15×30	15.2×30.2	0.556±0.030	221.6±19.6	548.8±8.7	110.5±4.2	109.9±5.1	110.1±4.8	222.9±19.5	0.121±0.011	261±6
18	18×31	18.6×31.3	0.520±0.023	209.0±12.0	427.7±7.7	110.6±4.3	110.2±4.3	110.4±4.3	210.3±11.9	0.089±0.006	259±14
19	16×30	16.1×30.8	0.368±0.026	162.2±10.6	458.4±17.8	163.1±5.3	162.8±6.3	162.9±5.9	164.0±10.7	0.070±0.006	362±4
20	14×30	14.3×30.7	0.385±0.026	162.6±10.8	540.6±17.5	159.8±5.7	163.5±6.5	161.9±6.4	165.0±10.8	0.088±0.007	371±6
21	12×30	12.1×30.4	0.405±0.027	166.7±11.7	663.6±25.0	164.7±5.8	162.9±5.8	163.6±5.8	169.6±12.0	0.111±0.0009	388±6
22	10×30	9.6×30.2	0.437±0.029	170.9±13.8	876.8±27.9	163.3±5.3	160.0±5.9	161.2±5.9	174.5±14.2	0.150±0.013	406±6
23	10×30	9.4×30.2	0.446±0.043	173.0±20.0	900.9±125.4	158.1±5.6	158.4±5.4	158.3±5.5	177.2±20.0	0.156±0.029	419±27
24	13×30	13.1×30.5	0.390±0.006	164.6±9.3	593.3±19.0	168.6±6.6	163.1±6.3	165.5±7.0	167.4±9.6	0.098±0.006	392±5
25	10×20	9.9×19.7	0.335±0.011	233.7±23.9	734.0±29.2	276.4±11.2	273.4±10.7	274.5±11.0	236.6±24.0	0.171±0.019	564±6
26	14×27	12.9×26.8	0.385±0.006	188.4±25.7	591.6±28.2	184.1±7.2	184.7±7.1	184.4±7.1	191.3±25.6	0.111±0.016	402±15
27	10×20	9.2×20.7	0.375±0.007	234.9±16.1	838.7±27.0	245.8±7.1	248.0±8.3	247.2±7.9	238.7±16.4	0.197±0.015	526±26
28	10×20	10.1×20.0	0.379±0.007	256.6±14.3	736.4±17.1	256.8±8.3	243.7±8.2	248.6±10.4	259.8±14.4	0.189±0.011	480±11
29	13×30	12.5×31.3	0.263±0.005	110.0±7.9	611.9±17.5	187.7±6.7	209.4±8.2	200.2±13.1	113.5±8.5	0.067±0.005	458±44
30	10×20	9.8×20.0	0.350±0.008	238.6±19.5	746.0±22.7	272.0±7.2	261.2±12.4	265.3±11.9	241.7±19.5	0.178±0.015	564±45

31	15×30	15.3×31.4	0.237±0.006	107.5±14.6	456.3±20.8	196.0±7.6	211.1±7.6	204.7±10.7	110.7±16.7	0.049±0.008	508±33
32	10×20	9.6×20.3	0.360±0.007	239.9±18.5	765.4±27.1	272.2±11.6	252.0±8.6	259.6±13.9	241.9±19.1	0.182±0.015	508±19
33	10×20	9.2×19.9	0.381±0.008	250.6±17.7	829.1±37.1	257.5±8.5	251.3±8.6	253.6±9.1	255.0±17.7	0.208±0.017	504±12
34	10×20	9.7×19.9	0.381±0.014	254.1±22.3	777.7±25.3	253.6±6.9	247.2±11.1	249.6±10.2	257.2±22.6	0.198±0.018	535±7
35	10×20	9.8×19.9	0.354±0.007	240.0±18.0	761.5±23.7	264.0±7.8	261.8±9.3	262.6±8.8	242.8±17.8	0.183±0.015	535±10

176 * Screens 2 to 22 were analysed by Álvarez (2010).

177 **2.2. Determining the aerodynamic characteristics of insect-proof screens**

178 The aerodynamic characteristics of insect-proof screens were determined by tests using a wind
179 tunnel (Fig. 3) designed at the University of Almería, Spain (Molina-Aiz *et al.*, 2006; Valera *et*
180 *al.*, 2006), with an improved control system (Espinoza *et al.*, 2015). The wind tunnel has a total
181 length of 4.74 m and a 388 mm diameter test section, where the insect-proof screen samples
182 were placed. Three tests were performed for each screen, with different, randomly selected
183 samples (Espinoza *et al.*, 2015; López *et al.*, 2018). The wind tunnel had a maximum speed of
184 10 m s⁻¹ and a maximum pressure drop of 200 Pa. These limits are set based on the air velocity
185 characteristics and the wind tunnel pressure drop sensors. The pressure drop was recorded by
186 two Pitot tubes (Airflow Developments Ltd, Buckinghamshire, UK; 4 mm of diameter) and
187 with a differential pressure transducer SI727 (Special Instruments, Norlingen, Germany;
188 operational range of 0-200 Pa and accuracy of ±0.25%). Air velocity and air temperature were
189 measured by a hot-wire anemometer EE70-VT32C5 (Elektronik, Engerwitzdorf, Austria;
190 measurement range of 0-10 m s⁻¹ and 0-50 °C; accuracy of ±0.2 m s⁻¹ + 2 % of measuring value
191 and ±0.2 °C). The technical characteristics of the wind tunnel and the control system used in
192 this study are described in Espinoza *et al.* (2015). For each sample, a test sequence with nine
193 increasing airspeeds or pressure drops was performed, followed by a sequence with nine
194 decreasing airspeeds or pressure drops.

Fig. 3. Wind tunnel used for the tests

195

196

197

198 Curves of pressure drop ΔP [Pa] as a function of air velocity u [m s^{-1}] were constructed for each
 199 insect-proof screen. Insect-proof screens are porous media from which their aerodynamic
 200 parameters can be determined: K_p , the screen permeability [m^2], is a coefficient that depends
 201 on the geometry of the porous medium, and is independent of the nature of the fluid (Nield and
 202 Bejan, 1999); Y , the inertial factor [dimensionless], a drag constant that depends on the
 203 characteristics of the porous material; F_ϕ , the pressure drop coefficient.

204 Airflow through a porous medium can be described by modifying Darcy's equation
 205 (Forchheimer, 1901):

$$206 \quad \frac{\partial P}{\partial x} = - \left(\frac{\mu}{K_p} u + \rho_a \left(\frac{Y}{K_p^{1/2}} \right) |u| u \right) \quad (1)$$

207 where P is the pressure [Pa], x is the airflow direction, u is the air velocity [m s^{-1}], μ is the
 208 dynamic viscosity of air [$\text{kg s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-1}$] and ρ_a is the air density [kg m^{-3}]. To calculate both μ and
 209 ρ_a it was necessary to measure the air temperature (Molina-Aiz *et al.*, 2004). Air temperature
 210 remained practically constant in each test (ranging from 19.8 and 25.5 °C). Some authors have
 211 used a second-degree polynomial to fit the experimentally observed pressure drop values as a
 212 function of the airspeed passing through the porous medium (Miguel *et al.*, 1997; Dierickx,
 213 1998; Muñoz *et al.*, 1999; Molina-Aiz *et al.*, 2006; Valera *et al.*, 2006). The zero-order term

214 can be neglected (Miguel *et al.*, 1997; Molina-Aiz *et al.*, 2009; López *et al.*, 2014), leading to
 215 the following equation:

$$216 \quad \Delta P = au^2 + bu \quad (2)$$

217 By matching the first and second order coefficients of Eq. (2) with Eq. (1), the screen
 218 permeability (K_p) and its inertial factor (Y) can be determined as follows (Molina-Aiz *et al.*,
 219 2009):

$$220 \quad K_p = e \frac{\mu}{b} \quad (3)$$

$$221 \quad Y = \frac{a K_p^{0.5}}{\rho_a e} \quad (4)$$

222 Applying Eqs. (3) and (4) requires knowledge of the thickness (e) of the screens. Another way
 223 of describing the relationship between the pressure drop and airspeed is to use Bernoulli's
 224 equation (Kosmos *et al.*, 1993; Montero *et al.*, 1997; Teitel and Shklyar, 1998):

$$225 \quad \Delta P = -1/2 F_\phi \rho_a u^2 \quad (5)$$

226 where F_ϕ is the pressure drop coefficient due to the presence of an insect-proof screen. The
 227 coefficient F_ϕ can be determined using Eqs. (1) and (5) since $\partial P/\partial x = \Delta P/e$ (Molina-Aiz *et al.*,
 228 2009):

$$229 \quad F_\phi = \frac{2e}{K_p^{0.5}} \left(\frac{1}{Re_p} + Y \right) \quad (6)$$

230 Below a specific Reynolds number limit, Teitel (2001) showed that the coefficient F_ϕ can be
 231 used to predict the pressure drop due to the screen. For a permeability-based Reynolds number
 232 (Re_p), the limit can be set to $Re_p < 10^5$ (Molina-Aiz *et al.*, 2009). The permeability Reynolds
 233 number (Re_p) can be calculated by (Nield and Bejan, 1999):

$$234 \quad Re_p = \frac{\sqrt{K_p} u \rho_a}{\mu} \quad (7)$$

235 Some authors have presented statistical models for predicting the value of F_ϕ as a function of
 236 porosity ϕ [$\text{m}^2 \text{m}^{-2}$] and Reynolds number (Re_d) based on the thread diameter (D_h) [m]: Eq. (8)

237 presented by Hayama *et al.* (2000) (in Bailey *et al.*, 2003), Eq. (9) by Pinker and Herbert (1967)
 238 and Eq. (10) by Bailey *et al.* (2003):

$$239 \quad F_\varphi = 28 \left(\frac{Re_d \varphi^2}{1-\varphi} \right)^{-0.95} \quad (8)$$

$$240 \quad F_\varphi = \left(\frac{13.0}{Re_d} + 0.82 \right) \left(\frac{1-\varphi^2}{\varphi^2} \right) \quad (9)$$

$$241 \quad F_\varphi = \left[\frac{18}{Re_d} + \frac{0.75}{\log(Re_d+1.25)} + 0.055 \log(Re_d) \right] \left[\frac{1-\varphi^2}{\varphi^2} \right] \quad (10)$$

242 The Reynolds number Re_d is calculated from the air velocity [m s⁻¹] and the thread diameter
 243 (D_h) [m]:

$$244 \quad Re_d = \frac{D_h u \rho_a}{\mu} \quad (11)$$

245 Another way of predicting the pressure drop in porous media is to use the equations presented
 246 in Nield and Bejan (1999) to estimate the K_p and Y values. The permeability (K_p) of the screen
 247 can be estimated from its porosity φ [m² m⁻²] and fibre thread diameter D_h [m]. This expression
 248 is known as the Kozeny equation (Nield and Bejan, 1999):

$$249 \quad K_p = \frac{D_h^2 \varphi^3}{\beta(1-\varphi)^2} \quad (12)$$

250 where β is a constant that depends on the type of porous material. The inertial factor Y can be
 251 estimated from the fibre diameter and pore size (Beavers *et al.*, 1973, Nield and Bejan, 1999),
 252 according to the following linear fit:

$$253 \quad Y = A + B \frac{D_h}{D_i} \quad (13)$$

254 in which A and B are two constants that depend on the type of porous material. In the case of
 255 insect-proof screens, we should use the thread diameter D_h and the inner pore diameter D_i .

256 Lastly, another method to estimate K_p and Y is to use the equations proposed by Miguel (1998)
 257 from the porosity φ [m² m⁻²]:

$$258 \quad K_p = 3.44 \times 10^{-9} \varphi^{1.6} \quad (14)$$

$$259 \quad Y = 4.30 \times 10^{-2} \varphi^{-2.13} \quad (15)$$

260 After determining the aerodynamic characteristics of the 35 insect-proof screens in the wind
 261 tunnel, the goodness of fit of the proposed models was analysed by comparing the
 262 experimentally observed values of F_ϕ (tunnel tests) with the corresponding estimated values of
 263 F_ϕ according to Eqs. (8), (9) and (10), and proposing alternative models for estimating F_ϕ . The
 264 goodness of fit of the proposed models was also analysed by comparing the experimentally
 265 observed results (tunnel tests) and estimated values of K_p and Y according to Eqs. (12) and (13)
 266 and Eqs. (14-15), and similarly proposing alternative models for estimating K_p and Y .

267 **2.3. Statistical analysis**

268 Regression analyses were used to compare the different variables to obtain statistically
 269 significant relationships (p -value < 0.05) using Statgraphics® Centurion 18 v18.1 (Statgraphics
 270 Technologies, Inc., The Plains, VA, USA). In addition to the correlation coefficient, R , other
 271 statistics were used to analyse the fit of the simulated (using different models) values of F_ϕ , K_p
 272 and Y to the experimentally observed values. Two of the most commonly used statistics for
 273 goodness of fit, based on the deviation of X_{sim} (simulated values) from X_{obs} (observed values)
 274 are the *RMSD* (root mean squared deviation) and the *MD* (or *bias*) (Kobayashi and Salam,
 275 2000):

$$276 \quad RMSD = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (X_{obs} - X_{sim})^2} \quad (16)$$

$$277 \quad MD = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (X_{obs} - X_{sim}) \quad (17)$$

278 The *RMSD* represents the average distance between the simulated and observed values. The
 279 *MD* corresponds to the mean value of the differences between the simulated and observed
 280 values, although in this case negative differences are compensated by positive ones, which may
 281 lead to an erroneous interpretation. Both statistics represent different aspects of the deviation
 282 from simulated values, but the relationship between is not been well defined (Kobayashi and
 283 Salam, 2000).

284 The Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency (*NSE*) is a normalised statistic indicating the relative magnitude
 285 of the residual variance of the model (“noise”) with respect to the variance of the observed
 286 values (“information”) (Nash and Sutcliffe, 1970). The *NSE* indicates how well a plot of
 287 observed versus simulated values fits the 1:1 line (Moriase *et al.*, 2007):

$$288 \quad NSE = 1 - \left[\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (X_{obs} - X_{sim})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (X_{obs} - \bar{X}_{obs})^2} \right] \quad (18)$$

289 where \bar{X}_{obs} is the average value of all X_{obs} values. The *NSE* can take values between $-\infty$ and
 290 1.0, the latter being the optimal value. Values between 0.0 and 1.0 are generally viewed as
 291 acceptable levels of performance (Moriase *et al.*, 2007).

292 Percent bias (*PBIAS*) represents the mean trend of simulated values to greater or lower than
 293 their respective observed values (Gupta *et al.*, 1999). The optimal value of *PBIAS* is 0.0, and
 294 values close to 0 indicate high model precision. Positive values indicate that the model provides
 295 values that are lower than those observed (model underestimation bias), whilst negative values
 296 indicate the opposite (model overestimation bias) (Gupta *et al.*, 1999). *PBIAS* can be expressed
 297 as a percentage:

$$298 \quad PBIAS = \left[\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (X_{obs} - X_{sim}) \times 100}{\sum_{i=1}^n (X_{obs})} \right] \quad (19)$$

299 *RMSD*-observations standard deviation ratio (*RSR*): this statistic standardises the values of
 300 *RMSD* with the standard deviation from the observed values (Moriiasi *et al.*, 2007). It combines
 301 both an error index and the additional information recommended by Legates and McCabe
 302 (1999):

$$303 \quad RSR = \frac{RMSD}{STDEV_{obs}} = \left[\frac{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (X_{obs} - X_{sim})^2}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (X_{obs} - \bar{X}_{obs})^2}} \right] \quad (20)$$

304 *RSR* takes values from 0 to a large positive value, and when *RMSD* is equal to zero, the model
 305 is considered perfect. Small values of *RSR* indicate better performance of the simulation model
 306 (Moriiasi *et al.*, 2007).

307 **3. Results and discussion**

308 Here, the results from the wind tunnel tests of the 35 insect-proof screens are presented. Two
 309 different models for estimating F_ϕ values as a function of different geometric screen
 310 characteristics are then presented, comparing the performance of these models with other
 311 models previously described in the literature. One model for estimating K_p values and another
 312 model for estimating Y values are presented and the performance of these models is compared
 313 with other models previously described in the literature. The effect of porosity on pressure drop
 314 predicted by the different models was analysed.

315 **3.1. Aerodynamic characteristics assessed in wind tunnel tests**

316 Table 2 presents the values of the aerodynamic parameters (K_p , Y and F_ϕ) for the 35 insect-
 317 proof screens tested in a wind tunnel.

318

319 **Table 2.** Aerodynamic characteristics of the insect-proof screens: a and b are the coefficients
 320 of the polynomial fit from the wind tunnel tests (Eq. (2)); R^2 , the fit determination coefficient;
 321 K_p , screen permeability [m^2]; Y , inertial factor; F_ϕ , pressure drop coefficient due to the presence
 322 of an insect-proof screen expressed as function of Re_p .

323 N : number of the screen.

N	a	b	R^2	K_p	Y	F_ϕ
1	2.784	3.045	0.9997	3.512×10^{-9}	0.233	$19.88 \times (Re_p^{-1} + 0.233)$
2	2.102	2.676	0.9928	4.041×10^{-9}	0.187	$18.74 \times (Re_p^{-1} + 0.187)$
3	2.036	2.253	0.9983	4.386×10^{-9}	0.206	$16.44 \times (Re_p^{-1} + 0.206)$
4	2.407	2.876	0.9988	3.576×10^{-9}	0.212	$18.95 \times (Re_p^{-1} + 0.212)$
5	1.767	1.676	0.9993	5.432×10^{-9}	0.216	$13.61 \times (Re_p^{-1} + 0.216)$
6	3.029	3.792	0.9976	2.731×10^{-9}	0.231	$21.84 \times (Re_p^{-1} + 0.231)$
7	2.985	3.235	0.9993	3.007×10^{-9}	0.254	$19.55 \times (Re_p^{-1} + 0.254)$
8	1.519	1.534	0.9997	6.461×10^{-9}	0.186	$13.58 \times (Re_p^{-1} + 0.186)$
9	1.879	3.074	0.9990	2.467×10^{-9}	0.186	$16.82 \times (Re_p^{-1} + 0.186)$
10	1.909	2.375	0.9987	4.484×10^{-9}	0.181	$17.52 \times (Re_p^{-1} + 0.181)$
11	1.845	1.876	0.9995	5.849×10^{-9}	0.194	$15.81 \times (Re_p^{-1} + 0.194)$
12	1.852	1.899	0.9990	5.835×10^{-9}	0.193	$15.99 \times (Re_p^{-1} + 0.193)$

13	1.947	2.176	0.9986	5.331×10^{-9}	0.185	$17.51 \times (\text{Re}_p^{-1} + 0.185)$
14	3.182	5.440	0.9992	1.716×10^{-9}	0.213	$24.83 \times (\text{Re}_p^{-1} + 0.213)$
15	3.595	6.006	0.9997	1.480×10^{-9}	0.235	$25.46 \times (\text{Re}_p^{-1} + 0.235)$
16	2.284	3.051	0.9994	3.211×10^{-9}	0.200	$19.05 \times (\text{Re}_p^{-1} + 0.200)$
17	0.870	2.635	0.9993	1.793×10^{-9}	0.118	$12.31 \times (\text{Re}_p^{-1} + 0.118)$
18	0.824	2.744	0.9992	1.713×10^{-9}	0.110	$12.51 \times (\text{Re}_p^{-1} + 0.110)$
19	2.235	4.738	0.9996	1.386×10^{-9}	0.192	$19.43 \times (\text{Re}_p^{-1} + 0.192)$
20	1.896	3.749	0.9997	1.798×10^{-9}	0.180	$17.52 \times (\text{Re}_p^{-1} + 0.180)$
21	1.575	3.179	0.9992	2.216×10^{-9}	0.159	$16.50 \times (\text{Re}_p^{-1} + 0.159)$
22	1.302	2.683	0.9993	2.745×10^{-9}	0.140	$15.50 \times (\text{Re}_p^{-1} + 0.140)$
23	1.261	2.645	0.9949	2.876×10^{-9}	0.134	$15.64 \times (\text{Re}_p^{-1} + 0.134)$
24	1.669	3.885	0.9995	1.853×10^{-9}	0.155	$18.20 \times (\text{Re}_p^{-1} + 0.155)$
25	2.562	4.159	0.9992	2.453×10^{-9}	0.187	$22.77 \times (\text{Re}_p^{-1} + 0.187)$
26	2.038	3.585	0.9994	2.028×10^{-9}	0.190	$17.84 \times (\text{Re}_p^{-1} + 0.190)$
27	1.913	1.844	0.9968	5.183×10^{-9}	0.218	$14.61 \times (\text{Re}_p^{-1} + 0.218)$
28	2.065	2.233	0.9949	3.926×10^{-9}	0.226	$15.33 \times (\text{Re}_p^{-1} + 0.226)$
29	3.886	5.802	0.9992	1.439×10^{-9}	0.269	$24.15 \times (\text{Re}_p^{-1} + 0.269)$
30	2.452	3.262	0.9992	3.154×10^{-9}	0.204	$20.10 \times (\text{Re}_p^{-1} + 0.204)$
31	5.872	6.111	0.9995	1.514×10^{-9}	0.377	$26.09 \times (\text{Re}_p^{-1} + 0.377)$
32	2.088	1.638	0.998	5.612×10^{-9}	0.255	$13.57 \times (\text{Re}_p^{-1} + 0.255)$
33	1.915	1.310	0.999	7.004×10^{-9}	0.266	$12.04 \times (\text{Re}_p^{-1} + 0.266)$
34	2.089	1.506	0.999	6.427×10^{-9}	0.260	$13.35 \times (\text{Re}_p^{-1} + 0.260)$
35	2.163	2.861	0.998	3.417×10^{-9}	0.199	$18.29 \times (\text{Re}_p^{-1} + 0.199)$

324

325 **3.2. Models for estimating F_ϕ values of an insect-proof screen with known geometric**
326 **characteristics**

327 To study greenhouse microclimate using computational fluid dynamic (CFD) simulations or
328 other types of mathematical simulation models it is necessary to know the aerodynamic
329 characteristics of the screens. Typically, insect-proof screen manufacturers do not provide the
330 aerodynamic characteristics or full geometric characteristics. Therefore, researchers often resort
331 to models such as those presented in Eqs. (8), (9), (10), (14) and (15) to estimate the
332 aerodynamic characteristics of the screens under study. For the screens analysed in this study,
333 alternative models were developed for estimating the values of F_ϕ , K_p and Y from different
334 geometric parameters.

335 From the F_ϕ expression determined using Eq. (6) (Table 2), F_ϕ values were calculated for each
 336 screen, at different values of airspeed u varying from 0.25 to 3.00 m s⁻¹, in +0.25 m s⁻¹ intervals.
 337 The maximum limit was set to 3 m s⁻¹ because this air velocity is unlikely to be reached in an
 338 insect-proof screen in a commercial greenhouse under natural ventilation conditions. The
 339 maximum values of air velocity observed near the vents of a commercial greenhouse with
 340 natural ventilation (side and roof vents) are normally unlikely to exceed 1.5 m s⁻¹ (Molina-Aiz
 341 et al., 2009; López *et al.*, 2012).

342 The first model, for estimating F_ϕ given the insect-proof screen porosity ϕ [m² m⁻²] and using
 343 a Reynolds number Re_d based on the thread diameter D_h [m], is presented in the following
 344 equation derived from the experimental observations (Fig. 4b):

$$345 \quad F_\phi = \left(0.481002 + \frac{11.5331}{Re_d}\right) \left(\frac{1-\phi^2}{\phi^2}\right) \quad (21)$$

346 with a 0.97 correlation coefficient, with a 93.9% R² and with a p -value<0.001.

347 This equation is similar to those reported elsewhere in the literature where the value of F_ϕ is
 348 estimated from a thread diameter Reynolds number (similar to Eq. (11)).

349 The second model developed is useful for estimating F_ϕ when the thread diameter is difficult
 350 to assess. From the experimental data (Fig. 4a), the equation was derived for estimating F_ϕ from
 351 porosity ϕ [m² m⁻²] and Reynolds number Re_t based on the screen thickness e [m] which is
 352 easier to measure with a micrometre:

$$353 \quad F_\phi = \left(0.475502 + \frac{26.2114}{Re_t}\right) \left(\frac{1-\phi^2}{\phi^2}\right) \quad (22)$$

354 This equation had a 0.96 correlation coefficient, with a 92.1% R² and with a p -value<0.001.

355 The Reynolds based on screen thickness [m] is:

$$356 \quad Re_t = \frac{eu\rho a}{\mu} \quad (23)$$

357

358 **Fig. 4.** Experimental $F_\varphi \cdot (1 - \varphi^2 / \varphi^2)^{-1}$ values expressed as a function of Re_t (a) and Re_d (b); the
 359 values of F_φ are calculated using Eq. (6).

360

361 Thus, Eqs. (21) and (22) allow values of F_φ exclusively to be estimated from geometric screen
 362 parameters and airspeed. Figure 5 shows the experimentally observed $F_{\varphi,obs}$ values calculated
 363 using Eq. [6] compared with $F_{\varphi,sim}$ values estimated using different models. For each screen
 364 presented in Table 1, and at different values of air velocity (u ; ranging from 0.25 to 3.00 m s⁻¹,
 365 in intervals of +0.25 m s⁻¹), F_φ values were estimated using previously published Eqs. (8)
 366 (Hayama *et al.*, 2000), Eq. (9) (Pinker and Herbert, 1967) and Eq. (10) (Bailey *et al.*, 2003) and
 367 using models proposed in this study Eqs. (21) (with porosity and Reynolds number based on
 368 thread diameter Re_d) and Eq. (22) (with porosity and Reynolds number based on the screen
 369 thickness Re_t). This figure shows that the $F_{\varphi,sim}$ values estimated using Eqs. (21) and (22)
 370 proposed in this study fit the observed $F_{\varphi,obs}$ values better than the $F_{\varphi,sim}$ values estimated using
 371 Eqs. (8), (9) and (10).

372

373 **Fig. 5.** F_φ values estimated using Eqs. (8) (a), (9) (b), (10) (c), (21) (d) and (22) (e) compared
 374 with experimental F_φ values (wind tunnel tests and with Eq. (6)).

375

376 Statistical analysis (Table 3) was also performed to identify the model for estimating $F_{\varphi,sim}$ that
 377 provides the values closest to the experimentally observed $F_{\varphi,obs}$ values. Both models presented
 378 in this study show significantly improved RMSD values with respect to models described in

379 the literature, reaching values of 18.9% (Eq. (21)) and 19.1% (Eq. (22)). In this case, the NSE
380 statistic reached 0.9 for Eqs. (21) and (22), almost equal to the optimal value, which is also an
381 improvement when compared with other models described in the literature (Eqs. (8), (9) and
382 (10)). The PBIAS statistic had negative values in the five models, which indicated that all
383 models overestimated the value of F_ϕ , providing values higher than the experimentally
384 observed values. However, the PBIAS values of the models presented in Eqs. (21) and (22)
385 were very close to the optimal value of zero, in contrast to the other three models. The RSR
386 values which can range from zero to ∞ , were also improved by the models presented in Eqs.
387 (21) and (22), with values closer to the optimal value of zero compared with the other models.
388 The results show that the models developed in this study (Eqs. (21) and (22)) provided $F_{\phi, sim}$
389 values that fitted $F_{\phi, obs}$ values better than the three models previously described in the literature.
390 The first model, (Eq. (21)) required the same geometric parameters as the other models
391 described in the literature; thus, to estimate F_ϕ values, the values of porosity and thread diameter
392 for the screens must be known. Conversely, to apply the second model (Eq. (22)), the values of
393 porosity and thickness of the screen must be known. This may be an advantage over the other
394 models because the process to measure the thickness may be simpler than measuring thread
395 diameter when it is not possible to obtain microscopic images. Measurement of the thread
396 diameter with a micrometer is difficult because of the non-cylindrical shape of the thread as
397 consequence of deformations that are produced during screen manufacture. However, the
398 measurement of the screen thickness with a micrometer is simple and more exact.
399 Equation (8) by Hayama *et al.* (2000) was derived for wire nets; in this case, these authors
400 worked with nine samples with 0.371, 0.504 and 0.778 porosity. The use of a metal wire net
401 and only a small number of samples are possible reasons for Eq. (8) estimated F_ϕ with
402 significant deviation from the experimentally observed values in our screen samples.

403 Equation (9), developed by Pinker and Herbert (1967) was derived originally using a small
 404 number of samples, with only 8 different samples of woven wire gauzes with porosity values
 405 ranging from 0.3 to 0.7 m² m⁻². These samples had a fabric structure similar to that of insect-
 406 proof screens. However, the material used (metal wire) was different from the polyethylene
 407 threads normally used today in insect-proof screens. These may be the reasons why this
 408 equation predicts F_ϕ values far from the experimentally observed values obtained here.

409 Equation (10), as used by Bailey *et al.* (2003), was derived by performing tests on 5 insect-
 410 proof screens with 0.25, 0.45, 0.53, 0.66 and 0.68 porosity. These porosity values are
 411 considerably different from the porosity values of the 35 screens used in this study, where
 412 porosity ranged from 0.237 to 0.556 m² m⁻². Of the 35 screens tested here, 29 had porosity
 413 values lower than 0.45 m² m⁻². This may explain why, that when using Eq. (10), the F_ϕ values
 414 assessed were also far from the experimentally observed values for our insect-proof screens.

415 Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended to apply an F_ϕ prediction equation that
 416 was derived using a sample of insect-proof screen as close to the example screen as possible.

417

418 **Table 3.** Statistical parameters of the comparison between experimentally observed $F_{\phi,obs}$
 419 values and $F_{\phi,sim}$ values estimated using equations proposed in the literature: Eq. (8) (Hayama
 420 *et al.*, 2000), Eq. (9) (Pinker and Herbert, 1967) and Eq. (10) (Bailey *et al.*, 2003) along with
 421 the equations developed in this study: namely Eqs. (21) and (22), R , the correlation coefficient;
 422 $RMSD$, root mean squared error; MD , $bias$; NSE , the Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency; $PBIAS$, percent
 423 $bias$; RSR , $RMSD$ -observations standard deviation ratio.

	Eq. (8)	Eq. (9)	Eq. (10)	Eq. (21)	Eq. (22)
R	0.970	0.974	0.979	0.970	0.960
$RMSD$	6.3	4.4	8.0	1.7	1.7
$RMSD$ (%)	69.6	49.0	89.1	18.9	19.1
MD	-1.9	-3.7	-5.4	-0.2	-0.2
NSE	0.2	0.6	-0.3	0.9	0.9

<i>PBIAS</i>	-19.0	-36.1	-52.7	-1.6	-1.8
<i>RSR</i>	10.4	7.3	13.3	2.8	2.9

424

425 Conversely, in general, these equations for estimating F_φ values have a higher error in
426 predicting F_φ for low air velocity values (Fig. 6). In the case of insect-proof screens, this is a
427 serious drawback because the air velocity through these screens in a greenhouse with natural
428 ventilation conditions is usually low, with maximum observed values of $\sim 1.5 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ (Molina-
429 Aiz *et al.*, 2009; López *et al.*, 2012). When using Eq. (8), 72% of the $F_{\varphi, sim}$ values have an error
430 $< 20\%$ of the $F_{\varphi, obs}$ value. When using Eqs. (9) and (10), only 12% and 11% of the simulated
431 values had an error $< 20\%$ of the $F_{\varphi, obs}$ value, respectively. However, when using Eqs. (21) and
432 (22), proposed in this study, 94% and 92% of the $F_{\varphi, sim}$ values had an error $< 20\%$ of the $F_{\varphi, obs}$
433 value, respectively. Castellano *et al.* (2016) used equations similar to those used here to predict
434 the aerodynamic characteristics of insect-proof screens with satisfactory results, but these
435 authors performed tests in a wind tunnels using air velocities $>4 \text{ m s}^{-1}$.

436

437 **Fig. 6.** Error observed between $F_{\varphi, obs}$ and $F_{\varphi, sim}$ (%) as a function of the air velocity. (a) $F_{\varphi, sim}$
438 assessed using Eq. (8) (\diamond) (Hayama *et al.*, 2000), Eq. (9) ($=$) (Pinker and Herbert, 1967), [10]
439 (\blacklozenge) (Bailey *et al.*, 2003). (b) $F_{\varphi, sim}$ assessed using Eqs. (21) (\times) and (22) (\circ).

440

441 **3.3. Models for estimating K_p and Y values of an insect-proof screen given their geometric**
442 **characteristics**

443 Another option for the aerodynamic characterisation of an insect-proof screen is to use the
444 screen permeability K_p and its inertial factor Y . Given these parameters, curves of pressure drop
445 as a function of air velocity of a screen can be constructed by applying the modified Darcy's
446 equation (Forchheimer, 1901), indicated in Eq. (1). These two parameters (Table 2) were
447 determined in wind tunnel tests for the 35 study screens. Previously, Miguel (1998) presented
448 two models for estimating the value of these two parameters from screen porosity (Eqs. (14)
449 and (15)). The constants β , A and B , in Eqs. (12) and (13) presented by Nield and Bejan (1999)
450 were also determined statistically for the 35 screens analysed in this study. This led to the
451 following equation for estimating the screen permeability K_p ($\beta=2.0679$) with the thread
452 diameter D_h [m] and porosity [$\text{m}^2 \text{m}^{-2}$]:

453
$$K_p = \frac{D_h^2 \varphi^3}{2.0679(1-\varphi)^2} + 3.8362 \times 10^{-10} \quad (24)$$

454 with 0.75 correlation coefficient, a 56.3% R^2 and a p -value < 0.05 . The following equation can
455 be used to estimate the inertial factor Y of the screen ($A = 0.0571195$ and $B = 0.135966$) with
456 the thread diameter [m] and the diameter of the inside circumference of the pore D_i [m]:

457
$$Y = 0.0571195 + 0.135966 \frac{D_h}{D_i} \quad (25)$$

458 with a 0.76 correlation coefficient, a 58.1% R^2 and a p -value < 0.0001 .

459 Figure 7 shows the values of K_p (a) and Y (b) estimated using the Eqs. (14) and (15) as a function
460 only of screen porosity proposed by Miguel (1998) and the Eqs. (24) and (25) obtained in this
461 study in the way proposed by Nield and Bejan (1999) as a function of porosity and geometric
462 characteristics of the screens, all of which are represented with respect to the experimentally
463 observed values (Table 2). This figure shows that the inertial factor (Y) values derived using
464 the equations by Miguel (1998) are much higher than the experimentally observed values and
465 that the permeability (K_p) values are much lower than the experimentally observed values. With

466 Eqs. (24) and (25) derived from the geometric characteristics of the screen as suggested by
467 Nield and Bejan (1999), the values similarly approximate the experimentally observed values.

468

469 **Fig. 7.** Simulated Y (a) and K_p (b) values compared to experimentally observed values. (Δ), Eqs.
470 (14) and (15) proposed by Miguel (1998); (\times), Eqs. (26) and (27) derived from the geometric
471 characteristics of the screens.

472

473 Statistical analysis was also performed (Table 4) to identify the equation(s) for estimating the
474 K_p and Y values that provide the closest simulated values to the experimentally observed values.

475 The equations proposed by Miguel (1998) for estimating the K_p and Y values provide values
476 very far from the experimentally observed values (Fig. 7 and Table 4). Therefore, in principle,

477 we advise against using these equations for several reasons. Miguel (1998) when developing

478 the model used only 14 screens. In addition, different types of screens were combined, 8 screens

479 with rectangular pores, similar to the screens used in this study, and 6 shade screens with

480 irregular pores made of a different type of fabric. Conversely, the equations of this study (Eqs.

481 (24) and (25)) were derived using more screens (35 in number), all of which were the same type

482 of fabric (weft and warp) with rectangular pores and with a narrow porosity range, from 0.237

483 to $0.556 \text{ m}^2 \text{ m}^{-2}$.

484 Based on the results, Eqs. (24) and (25) should be used to estimate K_p and Y values, in preference
 485 to the equations proposed by Miguel (1998) as a function of only the screen porosity. Equations
 486 (24) and (25), however, require knowledge of the thread diameter, the inner pore diameter and
 487 the porosity. Also, the screen thickness e must also be known to apply Eq. (1) and thus construct
 488 the pressure drop curve for the screen. In CFD software, a porous jump boundary conditions
 489 can be used to model screens (Molina-Aiz *et al.*, 2017) and filters knowing values of K_p , Y and
 490 e .

491

492 **Table 4.** Statistical parameters of the comparison between the experimentally observed $K_{p,obs}$
 493 and Y_{obs} values and the $K_{p,sim}$ and Y_{sim} values estimated using the Eq. (14) and (15) (Miguel,
 494 1998) proposed in the literature and Eqs. (24) and (25) based on the model proposed by Nield
 495 and Bejan (1999); *RMSD*, root mean squared error; *MD*, *bias*; *NSE*, the Nash-Sutcliffe
 496 efficiency; *PBIAS*, percent *bias*; *RSR*, *RMSD*-observations standard deviation ratio.

	K_p		Y	
	Eq. (14)	Eq. (24)	Eq. (15)	Eq. (25)
<i>R</i>	0.063	0.750	0.798	0.763
<i>RMSD</i>	3.240×10^{-9}	1.100×10^{-9}	0.220	0.025
<i>RMSD</i> (%)	92.9	31.5	107.9	12.1
<i>MD</i>	7.058×10^{-10}	3.487×10^{-9}	0.396	0.204
<i>NSE</i>	-2.8	0.6	-22.2	0.7
<i>PBIAS</i>	79.8	0.0	-87.1	-2.7
<i>RSR</i>	1.933×10^{-4}	6.561×10^{-5}	2.5	0.3

497

498 **3.4. Effect of porosity in the pressure drop estimation with the different models for** 499 **calculate F_ϕ , K_p and Y**

500 For the 35 screens (Table 1) and with the different values of F_ϕ , estimated using Eqs. (8) from
 501 Hayama *et al.* (2000), (9) from Pinker and Herbert (1967) and (10) from Bailey *et al.* (2003)
 502 along with Eqs. (21) and (22) derived from the present study, Eq. (5) can be used to obtain the
 503 values of pressure drop as a function of air velocity. In the same way, with the values of K_p and

504 Y estimated using Eqs. (14) and (15) (Miguel, 1998) and Eqs. (24) and (25) derived from this
 505 work from the general equations used for porous media (Nield and Bejan, 1999), Eq. (1) can be
 506 applied to obtain the values of pressure drop as a function of air velocity. Figure 8 shows the
 507 error (%) between the pressure drops measured in the wind tunnel ΔP_{obs} and those calculated
 508 from the different equations ΔP_{sim} as a function of the screen porosity. In Fig. 8a the error
 509 obtained with previous models of the pressure drop coefficient F_ϕ found in the literature is
 510 shown. In Fig. 8b the error obtained with the different models (two for F_ϕ and one using K_p and
 511 Y) can be seen.

512
 513 **Fig. 8.** Average error observed between ΔP_{obs} and ΔP_{sim} (%), for air velocities from 0.25 to 1.25
 514 m s⁻¹, as a function of the porosity of the screens. (a) ΔP_{sim} estimated using Eq. (8) (\diamond) from
 515 Hayama *et al.* (2000), Eq. (9) (\square) from Pinker and Herbert (1967), Eq. (10) (\blacklozenge) from Bailey *et*
 516 *al.* (2003). (b) ΔP_{sim} estimated using Eq. (21) (\times), Eq. (22) (\circ) and Eqs. (24) and (25) (\triangle).

517
 518 In general, the pressure drops calculated from models of F_ϕ obtained from the literature
 519 overestimated the measured values for all porosities ranging from 0.24 to 0.56 (Fig. 8a). The
 520 average errors for all porosities and velocities lower than 1.25 m s⁻¹ were 34.7% for Eq. (8),
 521 from Hayama *et al.* (2000), 35.5% for Eq. (9) from Pinker and Herbert (1967) and 63.3% for
 522 Eq. (10) from Bailey *et al.* (2003). However, the errors of the proposed models of F_ϕ , derived
 523 from porosity and the Re number obtained with the thread diameter (Eq. (21)) and the screen

524 thickness (Eq. (22)), appear to be uniform as a function of screen porosity, with average values
 525 of 5.2% and 4.4%, respectively.

526 Using the values of aerodynamic properties of the screens (permeability K_p and inertial factor
 527 Y) calculated with Eqs. (24) and (25), derived from porosity and two geometric characteristics
 528 of the screen (D_h and D_i), the average error was zero as consequence of an overestimation for
 529 porosities lower than 0.3 and underestimation for porosities greater than 0.5 (Fig. 8b).

530 Figure 9 shows the error (%) between pressure drop measured experimentally in the wind tunnel
 531 ΔP_{obs} and the pressure drop ΔP_{sim} calculated with the values of K_p and Y estimated using Eqs.
 532 (14) and (15) (Miguel, 1998) and Eqs. (24) and (25) derived from parameters presented by
 533 Nield and Bejan (1999). In Fig. 9 it can be seen how the models presented by Miguel (1998)
 534 provide a much higher error than the models obtain in this work for porosities < 0.5 , and similar
 535 errors for the two screens with porosities between 0.5 and 0.6.

536
 537 **Fig. 9.** Error observed between pressure drop measured experimentally in the wind tunnel ΔP_{obs}
 538 and calculated ΔP_{sim} (%) as a function of the porosity of the screens. ΔP_{sim} estimated using Eqs.
 539 (14) and (15) proposed by Miguel (1998) (\square) and Eqs. (26) and (27) derived from parameters
 540 presented by Nield and Bejan (1999) (Δ), using air velocities u ranging from 0.25 to 1.25 m s⁻¹
 541 ¹, in +0.25 m s⁻¹ intervals).

542 The errors of Figs. 8 and 9 correspond to the models obtained with new insect-proof screens
543 that have never been installed in a greenhouse. Once installed in the vents of the greenhouse,
544 and with the passage of time, the screens deteriorate and this can cause the screen to become
545 less rigid, increasing in thickness and reducing pressure drop (López *et al.*, 2018). On the other
546 hand, the accumulation of dirt causes an important increase of F_ϕ (between 16.5% and 61.2%;
547 for $u=1.0 \text{ m s}^{-1}$) and consequently increases in pressure drop (López *et al.*, 2018). These
548 contrary effects of material ageing and dirt accumulation on the aerodynamic characteristics of
549 screens must also be taken into account when applying the models described here.

550 **4. Conclusions**

551 Different models for estimating the aerodynamic characteristics of insect-proof screens, with a
552 weft and warp fabric, using one or more geometric parameters, were presented and validated in
553 this study. These models were generated from data obtained from 35 insect-proof screens with
554 porosity ranging from 0.237 to 0.556 $\text{m}^2 \text{ m}^{-2}$.

555 Two options were validated for estimating the pressure drop coefficient F_ϕ : the first model was
556 based on the screen porosity and a Reynolds number based on thread diameter and the second
557 model was based on the screen porosity and a Reynolds number based on thickness.

558 A third option was based on estimating the permeability K_p and the inertial factor Y . Two
559 equations were obtained for estimating the value of K_p as a function of thread diameter D_h and
560 porosity ϕ and for estimating the value of Y as a function of thread diameter and the inner pore
561 diameter D_i . These models have been shown to improve the accuracy of the previous models
562 described in literature that overestimated the pressure drops for all porosities analysed.

563 Models for aerodynamic parameters of the insect-proof screens K_p and Y based in their
564 geometric characteristics are very important to simulate the effect of this porous media in CFD
565 studies. Knowledge of K_p , Y and thickness allows to model insect-proof screens in CFD
566 simulations as a thin membrane using the porous jump model applied to a face zone.

567 Future studies should be orientated towards the development of more robust models and it
568 would be interesting to increase the porosity range and evaluate lower air velocities.

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574 **6. References**

575 Álvarez, A.J. (2010). *Estudio de las características geométricas y del comportamiento*
576 *aerodinámico de las mallas antiinsectos utilizadas en los invernaderos como medida de*
577 *protección vegetal*. PhD thesis. Almería, Spain: University of Almería, p. 423.

578 Álvarez, A. J., Oliva, R. M. & Valera, D. L. (2012). Software for the geometric characterisation
579 of insect-proof screens. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, 82, 134–144. [DOI:
580 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.compag.2012.01.001>]

581 Bailey, B. J., Montero, J. I., Pérez Parra, J., Robertson, A. P., Baeza, E. & Kamaruddin, R.
582 (2003). Airflow resistance of greenhouse ventilators with and without insect screens.
583 *Biosystems Engineering*, 86(2), 217–229. [DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1537-](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1537-5110(03)00115-6)
584 [5110\(03\)00115-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1537-5110(03)00115-6)]

585 Bartzanas, T., Boulard, T. & Kittas, C. (2002). Numerical simulation of the airflow and
586 temperature distribution in a tunnel greenhouse equipped with insect-proof screen in the
587 openings. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, 34, 207–221. [DOI:
588 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1699\(01\)00188-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1699(01)00188-0)]

589 Berlinger, M. J., Leblush-Mordechl, S., Fridja, D. & Mor, N. (1993). The effect of types of
590 greenhouse screens on the presence of western flower thrips: a preliminary study. *IOBC/WPRS*

591 *Bulletin*, 16(2), 13–16. [available online: <http://library.wur.nl/WebQuery/titel/843670>
592 (accessed on 1 June 2019)]

593 Beavers, G. S., Sparrow, E. M. & Rodenz, D. E. (1973). Influence of Bed Size on the Flow
594 Characteristics and Porosity of Randomly Packed Beds of Spheres. *Journal of Applied*
595 *Mechanics*, 40 (3), 655–660. [DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1115/1.3423067>]

596 Castellano, S. Starace, G., De Pascalis, L., Lippolis, M. & Mugnozza, G. S. (2016). Test results
597 and empirical correlations to account for air permeability of agricultural nets. *Biosystems*
598 *Engineering*, 150, 131–141. [DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2016.07.007>]

599 Dierickx, I. E. (1998). Flow reduction of synthetic screens obtained with both a water and
600 airflow apparatus. *Journal of Agricultural Engineering Research*, 71, 67–73. [DOI:
601 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1006/jaer.1998.0299>]

602 Espinoza, K., Valera, D. L., Torres, J. A., López, A. & Molina-Aiz, F. D. (2015). An Auto-
603 Tuning PI Control System for an Open-Circuit Low-Speed Wind Tunnel Designed for
604 Greenhouse Technology. *Sensors*, 15, 19723–19749. [DOI:
605 <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/s150819723>]

606 Fatnassi, H., Boulard, T., Demrati, H., Bouirden, L. & Sappe, G. (2002). Ventilation
607 Performance of a Large Canarian-Type Greenhouse equipped with Insect-proof Nets.
608 *Biosystems Engineering*, 82(1), 97–105. [DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1006/bioe.2001.0056>]

609 Fatnassi, H., Boulard, T. & Bouirden, L. (2003). Simulation of climatic conditions in full-scale
610 greenhouse fitted with insect-proof screens. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology*, 118, 97–
611 111. [DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1923\(03\)00071-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1923(03)00071-6)]

612 Fatnassi, H., Boulard, T., Poncet, C. & Chave, M. (2006). Optimisation of greenhouse insect
613 screening with computational fluid dynamics. *Biosystems Engineering*, 93(3), 301–312. [DOI:
614 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2005.11.014>]

615 Forchheimer, P. (1901). Wasserbewegung durch Boden [Water movement from ground].
616 *Zeitschrift des Vereines Deutscher Ingenieure*, 45, 1782–1788.

617 Gupta, H. V., Sorooshian, S. & Yapo, P. O. (1999). Status of automatic calibration for
618 hydrologic models: Comparison with multilevel expert calibration. *Journal of Hydrologic*
619 *Engineering*, 4(2), 135–143. [DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)1084-0699\(1999\)4:2\(135\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)1084-0699(1999)4:2(135))]

620 Harmanto, Tantau, H. J. & Salokhe, V. M., 2006. Microclimate and air exchange rates in
621 greenhouses covered with different nets in the humid tropics. *Biosystems Engineering*, 94(2),
622 239–253. [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2006.02.016>]

623 Hayama, S., Peng, G. & Ishizuka, M. (2000). Measurement of flow resistance coefficients for
624 wire nets in natural air convection flow. Proc. *Sixth Triennial International Symposium on Fluid*
625 *Control, Measurement and Visualization* (FLUCOME 2000), Sherbrooke, Canada, 13-17
626 August, 12 pp. [Available online:
627 [https://www.tib.eu/en/search/id/BLCP%3ACN071523984/Measurement-of-Flow-Resistance-](https://www.tib.eu/en/search/id/BLCP%3ACN071523984/Measurement-of-Flow-Resistance-Coefficients-for/)
628 [Coefficients-for/](https://www.tib.eu/en/search/id/BLCP%3ACN071523984/Measurement-of-Flow-Resistance-Coefficients-for/) (accessed on 1 june 2019)]

629 Kittas, C., Boulard, T., Bartzanas, T., Katsoulas, N. & Mermier, M. (2002). Influence of an
630 insect screen on greenhouse ventilation. *Transactions of the ASAE*, 45(4), 1083–1090. [DOI:
631 <http://dx.doi.org/10.13031/2013.9940>]

632 Kittas, C., Katsoulas, N., Bartzanas, T., Mermier, M. & Boulard, T. (2008). The impact of insect
633 screens and ventilation openings on the greenhouse microclimate. *Transactions of the ASABE*,
634 51(6), 2151–2165. [DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13031/2013.25396>]

635 Kobayashi, K. & Salam, M. U. (2000). Comparing simulated and measured values using mean
636 squared deviation and its components. *Agronomy Journal*, 92, 345–352. [DOI: doi:
637 <https://doi.org/10.2134/agronj2000.922345x>]

638 Kosmos, S. R., Riskowski, G. L. & Christianson, L. L. (1993). Force and static pressure
639 resulting from airflow through screens. *Transactions of the ASAE*, 36(5), 1467–1472. [DOI:
640 <http://dx.doi.org/10.13031/2013.28487>]

641 Legates, D. R. & McCabe, G. J. (1999). Evaluating the use of “goodness-of-fit” measures in
642 hydrologic and hydroclimatic model validation. *Water Resources Research*, 35(1), 233–241.
643 [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1029/1998WR900018>]

644 Linker, R., Tarnopolsky, M. & Seginer, I. (2002). Increased resistance to flow and temperature-
645 rise resulting from dust accumulation on greenhouse insect-proof screens. *ASAE Annual*
646 *International Meeting*, Chicago (USA), Jun 28-31, 9 pp. [DOI:
647 <http://dx.doi.org/10.13031/2013.10475>]

648 López, A., Valera, D. L., Molina-Aiz, F. D. & Peña, A. (2012). Sonic anemometry
649 measurements to determine airflow patterns in multi-tunnel greenhouse. *Spanish Journal of*
650 *Agricultural Research*, 10(3), 631–642. [DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5424/sjar/2012103-660-11>]

651 López, A., Valera, D. L., Molina-Aiz, F. D., Peña, A. & Marín, P. (2013). Field analysis of the
652 deterioration after some years of use of four insect-proof screens utilized in Mediterranean
653 greenhouses. *Spanish Journal of Agricultural Research*, 11(4), 958–967. [DOI:
654 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5424/sjar/2013114-4093>]

655 López, A., Valera, D. L., Molina-Aiz, F. D., Peña A. & Marín, P. (2014). Microclimate
656 evaluation of a new design of insect-proof screens in a Mediterranean greenhouse. *Spanish*
657 *Journal of Agricultural Research*, 12(2), 338–352. [DOI:
658 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5424/sjar/2014122-4956>]

659 López, A., Molina-Aiz, F. D., Valera, D. L., Peña, A. & Espinoza, K. (2018). Effect of material
660 ageing and dirt on the behaviour of greenhouse insect-proof screens. *Spanish Journal of*
661 *Agricultural Research*, 16(4), e0205, 12 pages. [DOI: [https://doi.org/10.5424/sjar/2018164-](https://doi.org/10.5424/sjar/2018164-11711)
662 [11711](https://doi.org/10.5424/sjar/2018164-11711)]

663 Miguel, A. F. (1998). Airflow through porous screens: from theory to practical considerations.
664 *Energy and Buildings*, 28, 63–69. [DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-7788\(97\)00065-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-7788(97)00065-0)]

665 Miguel, A. F. & Silva, A. M. (2000). Porous materials to control climate behaviour of
666 enclosures: an application to the study of screened greenhouses. *Energy and Buildings*, 31, 195–
667 209. [DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-7788\(99\)00010-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-7788(99)00010-9)]

668 Miguel, A. F., Van de Braak, N. J. & Bot, G. P. A. (1997). Analysis of the airflow characteristics
669 of greenhouse screening materials. *Journal of Agricultural Engineering Research*, 67, 105–
670 112. [DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1006/jaer.1997.0157>]

671 Molina-Aiz, F. D., Valera, D. L. & Álvarez, A. J. (2004). Measurement and simulation of
672 climate inside Almería-type greenhouses using computational fluid dynamics. *Agricultural and*
673 *Forest Meteorology*, 125, 33–51. [DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.agrformet.2004.03.009>]

674 Molina-Aiz, F. D., Valera, D. L., Álvarez, A. J. & Madueño, A. (2006). A wind tunnel study of
675 airflow through horticultural crops: determination of the drag coefficient. *Biosystems*
676 *Engineering*, 93(4), 447–457. [DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2006.01.016>]

677 Molina-Aiz, F. D., Valera, D. L., Peña, A. A., Gil, J. A. & López, A. (2009). A Study of Natural
678 Ventilation in an Almería-Type Greenhouse with Insect Screens by Means of Tri-sonic
679 Anemometry. *Biosystems Engineering*, 104, 224–242. [DOI:
680 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2009.06.013>]

681 Molina-Aiz, F. D., Norton, T., López, A., Reyes-Rosas, A., Moreno, M.A., Marín, P., Espinoza,
682 K. & Valera, D. L. (2017). Using Computational Fluid Dynamics to analyse the CO₂ transfer
683 in naturally ventilated greenhouses. *Acta Horticulturae*, 1182, 283–292. [DOI:
684 <https://doi.org/10.17660/ActaHortic.2017.1182.34>]

685 Montero, J. I., Muñoz, P. & Antón, A. (1997). Discharge coefficients of greenhouse windows
686 with insect-proof screens. *Acta Horticulturae*, 443, 71–77. [DOI:
687 <http://dx.doi.org/10.17660/ActaHortic.1997.443.8>]

688 Moriasi, D. N., Arnold, J. G., Van Liew, M. W., Bingner, R. L., Harmel, R. D. & Veith, T. L.
689 (2007). Model evaluation guidelines for systematic quantification of accuracy in watershed

690 simulations. *Transactions of the ASABE*, 50(3), 885–900. [DOI:
691 <https://doi.org/10.13031/2013.23153>]

692 Muñoz, P., Montero, J. I., Antón, A. & Giuffrida, F., 1999. Effect of insect-proof screens and
693 roof openings on greenhouse ventilation. *Journal of Agricultural Engineering Research*, 73,
694 171–178. [DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1006/jaer.1998.0404>]

695 Nash, J. E. & Sutcliffe, J. V. (1970). River flow forecasting through conceptual models: Part 1.
696 A discussion of principles. *Journal of Hydrology*, 10(3), 282–290. [DOI:
697 [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-1694\(70\)90255-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-1694(70)90255-6)]

698 Nield, D. A. & Bejan, A. (1999). *Convection in porous media*. (2nd ed.) New York: Springer.

699 Pinker, R. A. & Herbert, M. V. (1967). Pressure loss associated with compressible flow through
700 square-mesh wire gauzes. *Journal of Mechanical Engineering Science*, 9(1), 11–23. [DOI:
701 https://doi.org/10.1243%2FJMES_JOUR_1967_009_004_02]

702 Soni, P., Salokhe, V. M. & Tantau, H. J. (2005). Effect of Screen Mesh Size on Vertical
703 Temperature Distribution in Naturally Ventilated Tropical Greenhouses. *Biosystems
704 Engineering*, 92(4), 469–482. [DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2005.08.005>]

705 Taylor, R. A. J., Shalhevet, S., Spharim, I., Berlinger, M. J. & Lebiush-Mordechi, S. (2001).
706 Economic evaluation of insect-proof screens for preventing tomato yellow leaf curl virus of
707 tomatoes in Israel. *Crop Protection*, 20, 561–569. [DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0261-
2194\(01\)00022-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0261-
708 2194(01)00022-9)]

709 Teitel, M. (2001). The effect of insect-proof screens in roof openings on greenhouse
710 microclimate. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology*, 110, 13–25. [DOI:
711 [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1923\(01\)00280-5](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1923(01)00280-5)]

712 Teitel, M. (2007). The effect of screened openings on greenhouse microclimate. *Agricultural
713 and Forest Meteorology*, 143(3–4), 159–175. [DOI:
714 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.agrformet.2007.01.005>]

715 Teitel, M. (2010). Using computational fluid dynamics simulations to determine pressure drops
716 on woven screens. *Biosystems Engineering*, 105, 172–179. [DOI:
717 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2009.10.005>]

718 Teitel, M. & Shklyar, A. (1998). Pressure drop across insect-proof screens. *Transactions of the*
719 *ASAE*, 41(6), 1829–1834. [DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13031/2013.17336>]

720 Valera, D. L., Álvarez, A. J. & Molina-Aiz, F. D. (2006). Aerodynamic analysis of several
721 insect-proof screens used in greenhouses. *Spanish Journal of Agricultural Research*, 4(4), 273–
722 279. [DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5424/sjar/2006044-204>]

723 Valera, D. L., Belmonte, L. J., Molina-Aiz, F. D. & López, A. (2016). *Greenhouse Agriculture*
724 *in Almería. A Comprehensive Techno-Economic Analysis*. (1st ed). Almería (Spain): Cajamar
725 Caja Rural. [Available online: [http://www.publicacionescajamar.es/series-tematicas/economia/greenhouse-agriculture-in-almeria-a-comprehensive-techno-economic-](http://www.publicacionescajamar.es/series-tematicas/economia/greenhouse-agriculture-in-almeria-a-comprehensive-techno-economic-analysis/)
726 [analysis/](http://www.publicacionescajamar.es/series-tematicas/economia/greenhouse-agriculture-in-almeria-a-comprehensive-techno-economic-analysis/) (accessed on 1 June 2019)]
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Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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